

Growth Dynamics and Canopy Structures of Crop-Invasive Weeds Interaction Under Induced Salt Stress

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Submission: 18th Feb., 2025; Accepted: 9th March, 2025; Published: 23rd March, 2025

Abstract

Weeds cause a significant reduction in overall yield of many major agricultural crops. However, understanding crop-weeds interactions in salt induced salt stress is still debatable. This study examined the growth dynamics and canopy structures of *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) and *Capsicum annuum* (pepper) in mono and mixed culture with two invasive alien weeds (*Euphorbia heterophylla* and *Acanthospermum hispidum*) under different sodium chloride (NaCl) concentrations. Data for the study was obtained from field measurement and the parameters measured includes: plant height, number of branches, number of leaves, stem girth, and canopy spread. The results showed a significant variation in growth responses across different treatments. *Solanum lycopersicum* had the highest plant height at 5% NaCl with the value 71.20±2.20 cm in monoculture, while in *Capsicum annuum* plant height was highest in a mixture with *E. heterophylla* at 25% NaCl concentration. The number of branches was highest in the mixed *S. lycopersicum* and *E. heterophylla* at 20% NaCl with the value of 15.63±0.03 whereas the lowest value of 14.09±0.07 was recorded in the mixture of *S. lycopersicum* and *A. hispidum* at 15% NaCl. But in *C. annuum*, the highest number of branches was recorded in monoculture with the value of 16.02±0.04 whereas the lowest value of 15.01±0.03 was recorded in mixture of *C. annuum* and *A. hispidum* at 25% NaCl. The study concludes that mixed cultures acquire maximum light throughout their growth and developmental stage, indicating a suppressive hurdle faced by crops grown with weeds. Plant breeders are advised to develop resistance crop varieties to minimize the menaces caused by weeds.

Keywords: Canopy spread, crops, growth parameters, salt stress and weeds

1.0 Introduction

Biological invasion is a serious environmental concern and threat to agriculture, tropical biodiversity and can cause species extinction worldwide after habitat destruction and are recognized as one of the major ecological challenges of the 21st century [3]. The accumulation, establishment and subsequent spread of invasive species in non-native regions mainly occur as a result of global trade and travel activities which reported to have major negative impacts on agriculture, economic activities and human wellbeing [11], [8].

Agricultural activities such as crop cultivation, lumbering, as well as the extraction of medicinal plants have been reported to dominate the agroecosystem because of its high fertility that supports and allows the high yielding crops to be cultivated in the area [5]. However, those activities conducted in agroecosystem have promoted the growth of certain alien invasive weeds that reduces the regeneration of other crop plant species [23]. The importance and scope of the problem caused by alien invasive weeds are increasingly studied by many scientists worldwide that led to the convention on Biological Diversity to include the issue of alien invasive weeds among its main

sectorial themes with a strong objective of prevention and management of their introduction as well as their propagation [6]. Ecological integrity and biodiversity of agricultural ecosystems have been seriously threatened by expansion of invasive weed species across globe. The potential effects of invasive alien weeds species on global agriculture, which continues to affect food security globally, could be significant [7].

The economic cost of plant invasion to agriculture is growing due to the increasing number of new introductions which create a tremendous impact on crop production and reduce agricultural productivity by way of considerable mechanisms: competition for light, water, nutrient, allelopathy effects and decrease the crop yields and inhibition of seed germination [26]. However, the costs of their management to regulate the damages caused by invasive weeds reaches about \$336 billion USD (equivalent to # 554,880,000,000,000 NGN) in the US, Australia, United Kingdom, South Africa, and India alone and the menaces caused by them are increasing each day as the world becomes increasingly interconnected [21].

Generally environmental factors occurring in varying magnitudes will boost plant invasions globally, but its consequences could vary by region [12]. As species mechanisms have been well developed including morphological, physiological and biochemical adaptations to respond to different environmental factors such as drought and increased CO₂ that may promote invasion [10]. In addition, stress-tolerant species are already favoured in some areas in anticipation of changes triggered by climate change [17]. There is a large consensus in considering native plants more generally less tolerant to stresses than invasive alien species, thus having a lower plasticity in acclimatizing to environmental changes [31]. Similarly, [20], proposed that stress due to salinity, reduced levels of nutrients, water, and light reduces invasive success because exotic plants cannot tolerate the maximum levels of stress to which native species are adapted or in stressful conditions, the competitive balance between invasive weeds and crops is altered. However, [4], maintained that salinity can exacerbates the replacement of crops by invasive weeds [15], but salinity also can also restrain the spread and performance of some weeds [16]. Therefore, whether salinity can enhance the invasion of invasive weed species is debatable [10]. Therefore, this study examines crop-weeds interactions under induced salt stress in agroecosystem of Sokoto Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Sokoto is located in the extreme northwest of Nigeria, near the confluence of the Sokoto River and the River Rima. As of 2006, it has a population of 4,706,676. Sokoto town is the capital " of Sokoto State [18]. Sokoto experiences a hot semi-arid climate It is located in the dry Sahel surrounded by sandy Savannah and isolated hills with an annual average temperature of 28.3 °C (82.9 °F) and maximum daytime temperatures are generally under 40 °C (104.0 °F) for most of the year. The warmest months are February to April, when daytime temperatures can exceed 45 °C (113.0 °F). The highest recorded temperature is 47.2 °C (117.0 °F), which is also the highest recorded temperature in Nigeria. The rainy season is from June to October. Late October to February is the cold season where the climate is dominated by the harmattan wind blowing Sahara dust over the land [29]. 'Sokoto State is located in the savannah zone with a land area of 28,232.37 sq kilometers. It's located between latitudes 11° 30" to 15° 50" North and longitudes 4° to 6° East. It's bordered in the North by Niger Republic, Zamfara State to the North, and Kebbi State to the South and West [30].

2.2 Experimental site

A survey was carried out in Kurfi, Hamma' Ali and Dundaye agroecosystem of Sokoto State to determine weed species present (invasive weeds) in the area. A total of a four species (2 alien invasive and 2 crop species) were selected and grown in mono and mixed culture condition in the Botanical Garden of Kebbi State University of Science and Technology.

2.3 Plants collection and growing conditions

The seeds of crops namely *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Capsicum annuum* was purchased from Sokoto State Central Market, while the invasive weeds seed namely; *Euphorbia heterophylla* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* were collected from Dundaye agroecosystem of Sokoto State. The weeds were identified and authenticated by a taxonomist in the herbarium Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero, where voucher specimen (KSUSTA/PSB/H/VNO.328 PG and KSUSTA/PSB/H/VNO.331 PG) was deposited at the herbarium.

2.4 Experimental setup

Four (4) plots of 4m² of land were laid and harrowed in the Botanical Garden for seedbed preparation, both seeds were broadcast in each plot using a hand. Before the broadcasting, weed seeds were pre-soaked in a 70 °C hot water bath for 4 to 5 min, then dried at room temperature to increase germination rate [27]. The seedlings obtained from germination of the seeds in the seed bed, after two weeks when the seedlings developed 3 to 4 true leaves were transplanted in to the field laid out of 1m² in a randomised complete block design (RCBD). The treatments consisted of a factorial combination of two crops and two weed infestation levels arranged in crops-free and crops-weed mixture each respectively. To mimic salinity sodium chloride (NaCl) was applied to each plot replicated three times at concentration of 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25%, compositions respectively. The Plants were watered twice a week including those from the control treatment. After three consecutive applications NaCl at interval of two weeks, five plants from each of the trial plot was randomly selected tagged avoiding the border rows. These plants were used to measure growth dynamic and canopy structures progressively throughout the experiment. The parameters measured are as follows:

2.5 Plant height (cm)

A meter rule was used to measure the height of five (5) tagged plants in each experimental unit at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting and the mean value was calculated and recorded. The height was measured from the ground level to the tip of the plant [25].

2.6 Number of leaves per plants

Number of leaves from the five (5) tagged plants was counted in each experimental unit at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting and the mean value was calculated and recorded. Only fully opened leaves were counted [1].

2.7 Number of branches per plants

Number of branches from the five (5) tagged plants was counted in each experimental unit at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting and the mean value were calculated and recorded at every stage.

2.8 Leaf area (cm²)

Using the five (5) tagged plants leaf area were computed at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting by multiplying leaf (LL) length with leaf width (LW) and the product of coefficient factor ie., (LL* LW*CF) [22]. The leaf area was multiplied with the number of leaves per plant to get the leaf area per plant. The leaf area per plant was multiplied by the number of plants in plot to get the total leaf area of plant community in the area.

2.9 Leaf area Index (LAI)

The leaf area index was determined at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting as conducted by [2] and using equation 1.

$$LAI = \frac{\text{Total leaf area of plant community}}{\text{Land area occupied by the plant}} \text{ ----- eqn 1}$$

2.10 Stem girth (cm)

Stem girths were measured from five tagged plant using manual calipers at 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 weeks after transplanting.

2.11 Plant fresh weight (kg ha⁻¹)

The entire plants within the net plot area were uprooted washed and weighed. The value was extrapolated to per hectare.

2.12 Shoot fresh weight/plot (kg ha⁻¹)

Fresh weight of the shoot was obtained by separating the root from the plant and the shoot will be weighed using electronic weighing balance [2].

2.13 Canopy structure determination

The canopy structure was measured directly from canopy index as shown in equation 2. Plant height and canopy height of each plant was measured in the field every two week from the first measurement. Plant height was the length of the maximum vertical height of the main stem extended by hand, and canopy height was the height from the ground to the highest point of the growing plant in the stand. Canopy height was then divided by plant height to assess the longitudinal shape and inclination of the plant canopy, which may

determine the structure of the crop community in the field [13].

Canopy index (Cp) =

$$\frac{\text{Canopy height}}{\text{Plant height}}, 0 < Cp \leq 1 \text{----- eqn 2.}$$

The canopy index (Cp) may differentiate between plants in terms of their two-dimensional canopy structure. The maximum Cp is 1, which will be obtained in vertically growing plants. The index is a representation of structure and leaf compaction and stem and leaf inclination within the canopy, so that the larger the value of Cp, the straighter the plant shape.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Growth Variation and Canopy Spread of Mono and Mixed Culture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and Weeds

Table 1. compares the growth variations and canopy spread of *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) in mono and mixed culture with two alien invasive weeds at different sodium chloride concentrations. There was a variation in plant height obtained at all level of treatment but the highest value was recorded in monoculture at 5% concentration with the value of 71.20±2.20 and its significantly different whereas the lowest value in the was recorded at 15% concentration in the mixture *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* with the value of 48.80±1.40. This showed that moderate salinity levels may not adversely affect tomato growth in monoculture; however, higher salinity in mixed cultures can significantly reduce plant height. The number of leaves was higher in monoculture 10% monoculture with the recorded value of 54.14±3.40 whereas the lowest value was recorded at 25% in the mixture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* with the value of 35.48±1.50. This finding agreed with the findings of [14], who reported that increased salinity levels negatively impacted tomato growth parameters.

The number of branches were higher in the mixed culture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* at 20% with the recorded value of 15.63±0.03 while least value of 14.09±0.07 recorded at 15% in the mixture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* with the value of 0.0027±0.0002 and its significantly difference. The presence of certain invasive weeds and salinity levels can influence branching patterns. However, excessive salinity generally has a

detrimental effect on plant growth, as reported by [28], who observed that salinity stress adversely affects the growth rates and physiological characters of tomato plants. Similarly, [24], reported the lower total number of branches of Salmon peppers may be attributed to the fact that these plants had upright growth of their branches instead of the spreading nature as produced by other cultivars.

Moreover, the canopy spread was relatively higher in the monoculture at 15% concentration with the value of 1.25±0.04 whereas the lowest value of 1.06±0.05 was obtained in the mixture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* at 5% concentration and it's significantly different. The stem girth value was higher in the mixture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* with the recorded value of 1.19±0.03 while the least value was also obtained in the monoculture with the value of 0.86±0.01 at the same concentration and its significantly different. These findings indicates that salinity and crop-weeds interaction can significantly influence these growth parameters. [19] reported that salinity stress adversely affected the physiological responses of adult tomato plants, which could be associated with reduced canopy spread and stem girth

3.2 Growth Variations and Canopy Spread of Mono and Mixed Culture of *Capsicum annuum* and Weeds

Table 2 compares the growth variations and canopy spread of *Capsicum annuum* in monoculture and mixed culture with two alien invasive weeds at different concentration of sodium chloride. There was a variation in plant height obtained at all level of treatment but the highest value was obtained at 25% concentration of mixed culture of *Capsicum annuum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* with the value of 61.20±1.40 and whereas the lowest value in the was recorded at 20% concentration in the monoculture with the value of 37.60±2.10 and its significantly different.

The number branches were also higher in the monoculture with the recorded value of 16.02±0.04 whereas the least value was recorded at 25% *Capsicum annuum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* with the recorded value of 15.01±0.03. Similarly, number of leaves was higher in at 5% concentration in the monoculture with the recorded value of 46.30±3.50 whereas the least value was recorded at 25% in the mixture of *Capsicum annuum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* with the value of 35.48±1.50. This finding agreed with [19], who reported that salinity stress adversely affected the

physiological responses of adult tomato plants, which could be associated with reduced plant height and number of leaves. Moreover, the canopy spread follows similar trend with the above and was relatively higher in the monoculture at 10% concentration with the value of 1.34 ± 0.04 whereas, the least value of 1.09 ± 0.05 was obtained in the mixture of *Capsicum annuum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* at 5% concentration and it is significantly different. The stem girth value was

higher in the monoculture with the recorded value of 1.13 ± 0.01 while the least value was also obtained in the mixed culture of *Capsicum annuum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* at 15% concentration with the value of 0.61 ± 0.03 and its significantly different. This finding agreed with [19], who reported that salinity stress adversely affected the physiological responses of crop plants, which could be associated with reduced canopy spread and stem girth.

Table 1: Growth Variation and Canopy Spread of Mono and Mixed Culture of *Solanum lycopersicum* and Weeds

NaCl Conc (%)	Plant Height	No. of Branches	No. of Leaves	Leaf Thickness	Canopy Spread	Stem Girth
Control	78.45 ± 1.32^f	15.71 ± 1.02^g	55.23 ± 2.31^g	0.01 ± 0.001^a	1.23 ± 0.03^c	1.21 ± 0.02^k
S. 5	71.20 ± 2.20^e	14.70 ± 0.40^f	52.15 ± 3.10^{ef}	0.01 ± 0.00^a	1.24 ± 0.02^c	1.13 ± 0.01^{hi}
S. 10	67.70 ± 2.10^{cd}	14.38 ± 0.03^e	54.14 ± 3.40	0.01 ± 0.00^a	1.21 ± 0.06^{de}	0.86 ± 0.01^a
S. 15	68.13 ± 1.95^{cd}	14.09 ± 0.07^d	52.62 ± 1.70^{ef}	0.01 ± 0.00^a	1.25 ± 0.04^c	1.17 ± 0.01^{ij}
S. 20	68.83 ± 2.00^{de}	14.91 ± 0.02^{fg}	49.20 ± 2.50^e	0.01 ± 0.00^a	1.21 ± 0.03^{de}	1.09 ± 0.01^{gh}
S. 25	65.50 ± 1.95^c	14.76 ± 0.05^f	50.71 ± 3.20^{ef}	0.01 ± 0.00^a	1.23 ± 0.01^c	1.05 ± 0.01^{efg}
S and A 5	58.70 ± 1.40^b	13.70 ± 0.30^c	43.15 ± 1.50^{cd}	0.01 ± 0.01^a	1.06 ± 0.05^a	1.13 ± 0.03^{hi}
S and A 10	60.50 ± 1.40^b	13.38 ± 0.03^b	45.14 ± 1.50^d	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.14 ± 0.00^{bc}	0.86 ± 0.03^a
S and A 15	59.70 ± 1.40^b	13.09 ± 0.03^a	44.55 ± 1.50^d	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.14 ± 0.01^{bc}	1.17 ± 0.03^{ij}
S and A 20	58.60 ± 1.40^b	13.91 ± 0.03^{cd}	40.20 ± 1.50^{bc}	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.14 ± 0.00^{bc}	1.09 ± 0.03^{gh}
S and A 25	58.30 ± 1.40^b	13.76 ± 0.03^c	41.71 ± 1.50^{cd}	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.09 ± 0.05^{ab}	1.05 ± 0.03^{efg}
S and E 5	57.80 ± 1.40^b	15.32 ± 0.03^h	37.30 ± 1.50^{ab}	0.03 ± 0.01^b	1.09 ± 0.04^{ab}	0.97 ± 0.03^b
S and E 10	49.50 ± 1.40^a	13.76 ± 0.03^c	37.25 ± 1.50^{ab}	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.14 ± 0.04^{bc}	1.19 ± 0.03^j
S and E 15	48.80 ± 1.40^a	14.68 ± 0.03^f	36.78 ± 1.50^{ab}	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.14 ± 0.03^{bc}	1.16 ± 0.03^{ij}
S and E 20	50.60 ± 1.40^a	15.63 ± 0.03^i	36.05 ± 1.50^a	0.02 ± 0.01^b	1.17 ± 0.00^{cd}	1.03 ± 0.03^{def}
S and E 25	51.40 ± 1.40^a	15.01 ± 0.03^g	35.48 ± 1.50^a	0.01 ± 0.01^a	1.16 ± 0.00^{cd}	1.05 ± 0.03^{efg}

Values are means \pm standard deviation of three replications. Values within a column with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Keys: S= *Solanum lycopersicum* in Monoculture; S and A= *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* in Mixed cultures; S and E = *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* in Mixed cultures

Table 2: Growth Variations and Canopy Spread of Monoculture and Mixed Culture of *Capsicum annuum* and Weeds

NaCl Conc (%)	Plant Height	No. of Branches	No. of Leaves	Leaf Thickness	Canopy Spread	Stem Girth
Control	58.21 ±2.41 ^e	18.11 ±1.21 ^l	48.32 ±3.21 ^h	0.01 ±0.00 ^a	1.38 ±0.01 ^{bc}	1.15 ±0.02 ^o
C. 5	52.83±2.15 ^d	16.02±0.04 ^k	46.30±3.50 ^g	0.03±0.00 ^b	1.33±0.11 ^b	1.13±0.01 ⁿ
C. 10	41.17±2.15 ^b	14.76±0.03 ^f	46.25±3.10 ^g	0.01±0.00 ^a	1.34±0.04 ^{bc}	0.86±0.01 ^{gh}
C. 15	39.83±0.95 ^{ab}	15.68±0.05 ^j	45.78±3.20 ^{fg}	0.01±0.00 ^a	1.36±0.06 ^{bc}	1.17±0.01 ^p
C. 20	37.60±2.10 ^a	16.66±0.03 ^l	45.02±2.85 ^{efg}	0.01±0.00 ^a	1.38±0.04 ^{bc}	1.09±0.01 ^m
C. 25	38.20±1.90 ^a	16.01±0.02 ^k	44.48±3.10 ^{efg}	0.01±0.00 ^a	1.42±0.03 ^d	1.05±0.01 ^{lm}
C and A 5	52.90±1.40 ^d	15.24±0.03 ^h	37.30±1.50 ^{abc}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.14±0.04 ^a	0.81±0.03 ^{ef}
C and A10	50.60±1.40 ^d	13.76±0.03 ^a	37.25±1.50 ^{abc}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.14±0.04 ^a	0.68±0.03 ^{bcd}
C and A 15	51.90±1.40 ^d	14.68±0.03 ^e	36.78±1.50 ^{ab}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.16±0.00 ^a	0.99±0.03 ^{jk}
C and A 20	50.70±1.40 ^d	15.63±0.03 ^j	36.05±1.50 ^a	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.13±0.04 ^a	0.90±0.03 ^{hi}
C and A 25	47.40±1.40 ^c	15.01±0.03 ^g	35.48±1.50 ^a	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.18±0.01 ^a	0.91±0.03 ⁱ
C and E 5	58.70±1.40 ^e	15.66±0.03 ^j	43.71±1.50 ^{defg}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.09±0.05 ^a	0.77±0.03 ^c
C and E10	50.50±1.40 ^d	14.27±0.03 ^b	41.05±1.50 ^{cde}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.17±0.00 ^a	0.70±0.03 ^d
C and E 15	50.70±1.40 ^d	14.41±0.03 ^c	44.55±1.50 ^{efg}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.14±0.05 ^a	0.61±0.03 ^a
C and E 20	52.60±1.40 ^d	15.51±0.03 ⁱ	40.20±1.50 ^{bcd}	0.02±0.01 ^{ab}	1.16±0.00 ^a	0.64±0.03 ^{ab}
C and E	61.20±1.40 ^e	14.59±0.03 ^d	41.71±1.50 ^{def}	0.01±0.01 ^a	1.11±0.05 ^a	0.65±0.03 ^{abc}

Values are means ± standard deviation of three replications. Values within a column with different superscripts are significantly different (p<0.05). Keys: C = *Capsicum annuum* in Monoculture; C and A=*Capsicum annuum* and *Acanthospermum hispidum* in Mixed culture; C and E = *Capsicum annuum* and *Euphorbia heterophylla* in Mixed cultures.

4.0 Conclusion

The study concluded that the growth parameters of the crops varied significantly under different sodium chloride concentrations in both monoculture and mixed culture with the invasive weeds *Euphorbia heterophylla* and *Acanthospermum hispidum*. Monoculture showed higher growth performance in terms of plant height, number of leaves, and canopy spread, particularly at lower salt concentrations. However, in mixed culture conditions, especially with *Euphorbia heterophylla*, showed increased stem girth and branch number at higher salinity levels. Sodium chloride (NaCl) concentrations had significant effects on the growth and yield performance of the crops under both monoculture and mixed culture conditions. Canopy height was significantly higher in monoculture at 5% NaCl concentration, whereas the lowest value was recorded in mixed culture with *Euphorbia heterophylla* at 15% NaCl concentration,

indicating that salinity and competition from invasive weeds negatively influenced canopy development. Farmers and researchers can optimize crops growth and yield under saline conditions while mitigating the adverse effects of weed competition through implementation of soil monitoring and irrigation to prevent excessive salt accumulation, which could severely reduce yield

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